

The Crop Plant Scheduling Problem

Nikola Obrenović, Selin Ataç, Stefano Bortolomiol, Sanja Brdar, Oskar Marko, Vladimir Crnojević

Abstract With the increase in world population, the efficient production of food becomes an ever more important goal. One of the particular tasks associated with this goal is to find an optimal crop planting time, considering the allowed planting time windows and the following objectives: 1) weekly harvest must not surplus the available storage capacity and produce waste, and 2) the labor force should be utilized in the efficient manner. To tackle this problem, we define the crop plant scheduling problem (CPSP), in the form of mixed integer linear problem, and solve it with a commercial mathematical programming solver. To estimate the harvest time, we also predict the time needed for accumulation of the sufficient amount of growing degree units (GDUs), using an ARIMA model. In this paper, we present the developed GDU forecasting and CPSP models, and the obtained results for the two selected problem instances.

1 Introduction

Due to the global population increase and expansion of urban and industrial areas, the arable land area per inhabitant of our planet is decreasing [5]. Therefore, we can expect food to become a very scarce and valuable resource and optimization of its production process a very important topic. One aspect of food production is to satisfy the demand without creating a surplus which cannot be consumed and represents a waste.

Nikola Obrenović, Sanja Brdar, Oskar Marko, Vladimir Crnojević
University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute, Dr Zorana Đinđića 1, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia,
e-mail: {nikola.obrenovic, sanja.brdar, oskar.marko, crnojevic}@biosense.rs

Selin Ataç, Stefano Bortolomiol
École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Transport and Mobility Laboratory (TRANSP-OR),
GC B2 385, Lausanne, CH-1015, Switzerland,
e-mail: {selin.atac, stefano.bortolomiol}@epfl.ch

Many crop types are important elements in the production of various food and industrial products, which sets a goal for the producers to harvest as many crops as possible. However, the produced crops need to be stored appropriately until forwarded further in the process chain. Therefore, it is important not to overflow the available storage capacities and avoid waste of produced crop. This has led to the definition of the crop plant scheduling problem (CPSP) with the main objective to produce the required amount of crop, distributed over the time horizon, in order to avoid exceeding the available storage capacity whenever possible. Additionally, the engagement of labor force should be taken into account and managed properly. This is reflected by setting two additional goals for our problem, namely

1. to harvest all crops in the minimum number of weeks and
2. to avoid gaps in harvest, which represent weeks when the employees are paid although there is no work required.

From the moment of planting, crop seeds start growing thanks to the accumulation of heat, which can be measured in growing degree units (GDUs). Then, when a predetermined amount of GDUs is reached, plants are harvested. We denote as crop population each group of seeds, which are located at the same plantation site and which are planted and harvested at the same time. The accumulation of GDUs depends on the planting site and varies throughout the year. Therefore, given a time window of possible planting dates for each population, it is first necessary to estimate the harvest date of each crop population for each feasible planting date. For this purpose, we estimate the dates of acquiring the sufficient amount of GDUs per population by creating an ARIMA model [3] to forecast the daily GDUs based on historical data.

The presented optimization problem, in its lesser form, has been first introduced in the Syngenta Crop Challenge in Analytics 2021 [12]. Since the CPSP still represents an open research challenge, we continue to work on its solution even after the Syngenta competition.

The remaining of the paper is organized in the following manner. The related literature is presented in Section 2. The GDUs forecasting model, data preprocessing, and CPSP definition are described in Section 3. The selected problem instances and their solutions are presented in Section 4. The conclusions and future research paths are given in Section 5.

2 Related literature

In the literature, we have found thus far only one similar problem, i.e., the crop growth planning problem in vertical farming [11]. There, the authors propose a linear programming solution approach. The modeling approach in [11] is based on a time-expanded network and their model structure resembles the multicommodity flow models [2], as stated by the authors themselves. Consequently, their model is considerably different from ours.

We also observe that the CPSP possesses similarities with the well-known job shop scheduling [9] and batch plant scheduling processing problems [13]. The analogy lies in the fact that each crop population requires certain time to grow, which is analogous to job execution time, while the number of simultaneously cultivated populations is limited by the storage capacity, corresponding to the machines' capacities. The mentioned problems are known to be \mathcal{NP} -hard [6, 13]. Therefore, in the case of large instances, these problems are solved by heuristic approaches, such as simulated annealing [9], neighborhood searches [6], and genetic algorithms [13]. Similarly, we intend to consider these methods in our future research, too.

To conclude, we have not found a similar optimization problem in the literature, which possesses the characteristics of CPSP. Hence, the development of a new optimization model is justified.

3 Methodology

At the highest level, the selected methodological approach can be divided into three main components:

1. forecasting of the GDUs,
2. data preparation for the optimization model, and
3. optimization of the planting schedule based on the forecasted GDUs.

The first is based on an ARIMA model and performed independently from the planting schedule optimization.

GDUs forecasting is described in detail in Subsection 3.1. Data preprocessing and planting schedule optimization model are presented in Subsections 3.2 and 3.3, respectively.

3.1 Growing Degree Units Forecasting

As input for GDU forecasting, we use the historical data about daily accumulated GDUs, for the period of previous 10 years. With that, we predict the obtained GDUs in the following 80 weeks, which represent the planning horizon of the subsequent optimization problem.

To analyze the input data, we apply Error, Trend, and Seasonality (ETS) decomposition of the time series data (Figure 1). From the figure, we observe that the time series have a seasonality component. As a result, the data is not stationary.

Because of the seasonality, forecasting methods such as simple exponential smoothing or double exponential smoothing do not work [7]. Therefore, we focus on an autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model [3].

To determine the parameters of the $\text{ARIMA}(p, d, q)$ model, where p , d , and q denote the autoregressive, differencing, and moving average parameters, respectively,

Fig. 1 ETS decomposition of historical GDU data

we refer to Box-Jenkins method [3]. First, we come up with the auto-correlation function (ACF) and partial auto-correlation function (PACF) of the time series (Figure 2). From Figure 2, we observe the cut off lag in PACF, which provides the maximum value for the autoregressive parameter $p = 4$. Similarly, the cut off lag in ACF suggests the moving average parameter q to be set to value 3 at most. From ACF plot, we also determine the differencing parameter $d = 1$, as the lag after which autocorrelations drop significantly.

Further, we take advantage of Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC, [8]) in order to find the best parameters among several candidates. Since we are interested in the simplest model, we compare the AIC values of ARIMA(4,1,3) model and all other simpler models, such as ARIMA(1,1,1) and ARIMA(1,1,2). We find that the minimum AIC value is achieved for ARIMA(2,1,2).

Therefore, we use the ARIMA(2,1,2) model to forecast the accumulated GDUs per day for the time period of 80 weeks.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

Each crop population is described by the estimated harvest quantity, required GDUs, initially planned planting date, and a planting time window, expressed in weeks of the

Fig. 2 ACF and PACF plots

planning horizon. The output of the ARIMA model provides the GDU forecast for the time horizon for planting site per day. However, to improve model performance, we accumulate the obtained GDUs on a weekly level, i.e., we calculate the amount of GDUs accumulated up to week w . From the planting time windows information for each population, we come up with a feasible set of combinations of population p and harvest week w , denoted as F . The harvest date is assumed to be on any day of the targeted week.

This preprocessing allows us to define the optimization model based on harvest weeks, as presented in the following subsection. With that, we avoid explicit modeling of plant weeks and simplify the optimization problem without loss of generality. When the harvest week is determined, we backtrack the possible plant weeks. Furthermore, this approach prevents from accumulating too many more GDUs than required.

3.3 Mathematical model

The CPSP represents a multi-objective problem. The elements of the constructed mathematical model are presented here after.

Sets

- P the set of corn populations
 W the weeks of the planning horizon
 $F = \{(p, w)\}$ the set of feasible combinations of population p and harvest week w

Data

- Q_p the expected yield of crop population p
 C the storage capacity

Indices

- $p \in \{1, \dots, |P|\}$ the population id
 $w \in \{1, \dots, |W|\}$ the week id

Decision variables

- h_{pw} binary variable determining if population p is harvested in week w
 u_w binary variable determining if week w is used for harvesting

Objectives

$$\min f_1 = \sum_{w \in W} \left| \sum_{p \in P} h_{pw} Q_p - C \right| \quad (1)$$

$$\min f_2 = \sum_{w \in W} u_w \quad (2)$$

$$\min f_3 = \sum_{w \in \{1..|W|-1\}} |u_{w+1} - u_w| \quad (3)$$

Objective (1) minimizes the total deviation from the capacity for all weeks. Objective (2) minimizes the number of weeks used for harvesting. This objective serves the aim of shortening the time horizon needed to harvest all populations. Lastly, objective (3) strives to consolidate harvest weeks into consecutive weeks to minimize the workforce fluctuation.

In the final model version, the objectives are combined by using the weighted sum:

$$\min z = f_1 + c \cdot f_2 + c \cdot f_3. \quad (4)$$

The weight c for objectives (2) and (3) is set to be equal to the storage capacity value.

Constraints

$$\sum_{w:(p,w) \in F} h_{pw} = 1 \quad \forall p \in P \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{w \in W} h_{pw} = 1 \quad \forall p \in P \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{p:(p,w) \in F} h_{pw} \leq u_w \cdot M_1 \quad \forall w \in W \quad (7)$$

$$h_{pw} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in P, w \in W \quad (8)$$

$$u_w \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall w \in W \quad (9)$$

The constraint set (5) ensures that each population is harvested in one of the feasible weeks, whilst constraints (6) ensure that a population is harvested in no more than one week. Constraints (7) determine which weeks are used for harvesting. Here, M_1 is a *big-M* value that is set to the maximum possible number of populations harvested in any of the weeks of planning horizon. The rest of the constraints, i.e., (8) and (9), are domain constraints.

The expressions of absolute value of differences in objectives (1) and (3) are linearized with the technique explained in [1], which leads to the introduction of the following variable sets:

- ey_w^+ - the yield deviation above the capacity in the harvesting week w ,
- ey_w^- - the yield deviation below the capacity in the harvesting week w ,
- ew_w^+ - the indicator of change from non-harvesting w to harvesting week $w + 1$,
and
- ew_w^- - the indicator of change from harvesting w to non-harvesting week $w + 1$.

Additionally, we apply another coefficient, $k > 1$, at the surplus over the storage capacity in order to emphasize that positive deviation from the capacity is less favorable than the negative one. Finally, we obtain the following linear model:

$$\min z = \sum_{w \in W} (k \cdot ey_w^+ + ey_w^-) + c \sum_{w \in W} u_w \quad (10)$$

$$+ c \sum_{w \in \{1..|W|-1\}} (ew_w^+ + ew_w^-) \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{w: (p,w) \in F} h_{pw} = 1 \quad \forall p \in P \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{w \in W} h_{pw} = 1 \quad \forall p \in P \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{p \in P} h_{pw} \leq u_w \cdot M_1 \quad \forall w \in W \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{w \in W} Q_p h_{pw} - C = ey_w^+ - ey_w^- \quad \forall w \in W \quad (15)$$

$$u_{w+1} - u_w = ew_w^+ - ew_w^- \quad \forall w \in W \quad (16)$$

$$h_{pw} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall p \in P, w \in W \quad (17)$$

$$u_w \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall w \in W \quad (18)$$

$$ey_w^+ \geq 0 \quad \forall w \in W \quad (19)$$

$$ey_w^- \geq 0 \quad \forall w \in W \quad (20)$$

$$ew_w^+ \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall w \in W \quad (21)$$

$$ew_w^- \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall w \in W \quad (22)$$

4 Results

The model has been tested on two problem instances, which have been created based on the instances provided at the Syngenta Crop Analytics Challenge 2021 [12]:

1. Instance 1 contains 1375 different corn populations which need to be planted in the period of one year. The harvest horizon ends within 80 weeks from the year start. The storage capacity is set to 7000 units.
2. Instance 2 contains 1194 corn populations, while the harvest horizon ends within 71 weeks from the year start. The storage capacity is 6000 units.

Problem instances are solved with IBM ILOG CPLEX ver. 12.9 on Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-9400 processor at 2.90GHz, with 16GB RAM,

For Instance 1, the optimal solution is reached in 28.67 seconds. Figure 3 shows the harvest schedules and quantities of the experience-based and resulting solutions, with blue and orange bars, respectively. The experience-based solution is determined by the planting days defined by an expert, for each crop population. The storage capacity is presented with the dashed black line.

Fig. 3 Expert-defined and optimal solution schedules for data instance 1

From Figure 3, we observe that the storage capacity is always satisfied in week 17 and starting from week 40, while the harvest weeks are mainly condensed in two chunks, from week 17 to week 45 and from week 56 till week 69, with the exception of weeks 50 and 51.

For weeks 18 to 39, we have tried to reduce the created surplus by further constraining the harvest amount. However, in this case, the problem becomes infeasible

which brings us to the conclusion that we cannot further reduce surplus with this particular data instance.

Instance 2 is solved optimally in 324.28 seconds. Similarly, Figure 4 shows the expert-defined harvest schedule and the schedule of the optimal solution, with blue and orange bars, respectively. The storage capacity is presented with the dashed black line.

Fig. 4 Expert-defined and optimal solution schedules for data instance 2

The optimal solution of Instance 2 schedules all harvests in consecutive weeks 17 to 61, without having wasted surplus in any of the weeks. This solution demonstrates clearly the quality potential of our proposed model.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we present the crop plant scheduling problem (CPSP), whose goal is to reduce the wasted production surplus and cleverly utilize the workforce. The problem is modeled as a mixed integer linear program and solved for two instances inspired by the Syngenta Crop Analytics Challenge 2021 [12] by using a commercial mathematical programming solver. To be able to estimate crop populations harvest times, we also develop and present here an ARIMA model of the GDUs gathered during the planning horizon. The obtained results show the strength and practical potential of the defined model.

In our future work, we intend to create more synthetic, however realistic, test data sets, in cooperation with industry partners, for the purpose of evaluating the proposed model thoroughly. Larger data instances will also be considered and might eventually require development of heuristic or metaheuristic solution approaches, based on, e.g., adaptive large neighborhood search [10] and NSGA-II [4].

In this work, the forecast of obtained GDUs is done only with one model, while in the future we plan to test some additional forecasting techniques. Therefore, we also intend to develop a robust optimization approach, which will account for the estimated error of GDU forecast and multiple forecasting models.

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